

Improving Staff Communication through Foreign Language Training on the Kanto Lampo Waterfall Tourist Attraction

I Nyoman Winia¹, Ni Nyoman Triyuni², Nyoman Mastiani Nadra³, Ni Putu Lianda Ayu Puspita⁴,
Luh Putu Candra Aprilia Dewi⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} Politeknik Negeri Bali, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: In 2 years (covid outbreak) the Kanto Lampo Waterfall tourist attraction has not been operational resulting in many things changing and not being maintained. The results of discussions with management can be seen that there are 3 problems, namely: (1) Tourism human resources are very important to understand and have expertise, health and work safety (K3), (2) Human resources need to also master several foreign languages besides English considering that tourists come from various countries; Thus, the solution that can be offered is K3 training to increase skills in handling tourists and foreign languages. Training is provided by lecturers who are competent in their fields. Training runs according to a predetermined schedule. The results of the activity showed that K3 training had increased understanding to 100%. The results of foreign language training also increased to 87% and grammar use by 90%. From the interview results, the training was said to be satisfactory. This can be indicated by the request of participants and management to carry out further activities with the addition of excellent service and management training so that management can be carried out more professionally.

KEYWORDS: Foreign Languages, Tourist Attractions, Waterfalls

INTRODUCTION

Tourism activities still greatly contribute to the diversification of the local economy, especially the multiplier effect. This is thanks to government intervention which always improves tourist destination areas by exploring new things in tourist destination areas (Barros et al., 2011). Tourism is always a hot topic of conversation because of the emergence of new tourist attractions. This is because many interesting places are starting to be managed as tourist attractions. Talking about tourism cannot be separated from Bali tourism. Even though Bali already has an international name, Bali is always improving and adding new tourist attractions so that tourists visiting Bali have many choices. This is in line with the opinion of Haryanto (2020) who states that tourists who travel do not only want to gain new experiences but with a very dominant recreational purpose (Haryanto, 2020).

In the Bali Provincial Regulation Number 5 of 2020 concerning Standards for the Implementation of Balinese Cultural Tourism, it is stated that a tourist attraction is something that has uniqueness, beauty and value in the form of a diversity of natural, cultural, spiritual and man-made wealth that is targeted or destination for tourist visits. One of them is a waterfall tourist attraction.

The tourist attraction of waterfalls is currently becoming a favorite, so many waterfall tourist attractions have emerged almost all over the world. Waterfalls are one of the most spectacular shows put on in nature, a constant attraction for tourists. Seeking their special beauty, waterfalls are enchanting due to the large volume of water, the height of the waterfall, the number of steps, and the roar of the noise and, last but not least, because of the unique landscape in which this natural show is played (Băţinaş, 2010). Waterfalls offer spectacular natural attractions that provide various attractions for tourists, for example beautiful views, waterfall phenomena, vegetation, fresh air and outdoor experiences (Prasetyo & Retnaningdyah, 2017). Waterfall is one of the natural resources which are widely explored by tourism planners and managers as tourism destinations, even many tourists feel delight when visiting the waterfall tourist attraction. In fact, tourists like this are often referred to as waterfall lovers, fans, buffs, and collectors because they collect photos of their activities at the waterfall (Hudson, 2013).

Tourist attraction management must also upgrade its management and/or staff so that the services provided are optimal. Upgrading can be done through collaboration with universities because one of the principles of higher education's tridharma is to carry out community service. This was also stated by Gruescu & Tanasie (2009) that industry will be able to increase its responsibility to prepare employees at all levels and companies can increase and maintain their commitment. Universities as educational institutions have an important role in improving and developing quality human resources for development needs. This can be implemented

through community service programs. It is further said that community service can be carried out through community education and training, community service, and reviewing the actions of science and technology produced by universities. The aim of this program is to apply the results of science and technology for community empowerment so as to produce changes in the knowledge, skills and attitudes of the target community group (Noor, 2010).

Community service carried out by the Bali State Polytechnic college through the Tourism Business Management Study Program, Department of Tourism, was carried out at the international tourist attraction Kanto Lampo Waterfall which is located in Beng Gianyar village. Kanto Lampo waterfall is in a lowland area so it can be reached easily. Kanto Lampo waterfall has its own uniqueness because there is a temple as a holy place that can be used for painting and across the river there is a Dutch heritage cave as an additional tourist attraction. 2022 is a milestone for the revival of tourism in Indonesia and Bali. Apart from accommodation, the attraction is also starting to improve and reorganize its operations. 2023 is a promising year for tourist attractions in Bali. One of the tourist attractions is the Kanto Lampo Gianyar Waterfall.

In 2 years (covid outbreak) the Kanto Lampo Waterfall tourist attraction was not operational, resulting in many things changing and not being maintained. This means that there are many things that must be improved both in terms of human resources (HR) and the environment of the tourist attraction itself. HR also needs to master several foreign languages besides English considering that tourists come from various countries. Foreign language training is required to handle visiting tourists at the entrance. However, if HR can master several foreign languages then the task of taking you to the waterfall can be taken over so that the ticket cost includes delivery to the waterfall. Foreign language training can be provided by taking over the delivery of tourists to the waterfall so that the driver/guide can rest. This will be a special promotion for the drivers and guides and they will feel cared for.

When someone has to communicate with people from other countries who have different languages, mastery of the foreign language so that both can understand each other is an absolute must (Setyanto & Litt, 2014).

Mastery of a foreign language is also important to increase tourist satisfaction, because information provided in good language can be accepted. By mastering a foreign language, communication will run smoothly and in two directions. Therefore, communication is a skill that workers in the tourism sector must master, especially being able to master both spoken and written language (Erhan, 2014).

This community service activity was carried out at the Kanto Lampo waterfall tourist attraction. The method for implementing this activity is a participatory method in the form of training and assistance when providing services to tourists. The level of knowledge is obtained through combining the results of the pretest and posttest, as well as monitoring staff when serving tourists.

METHODS

Analysis was carried out using qualitative descriptive analysis of data obtained from the activity location. All results of data analysis are presented both formally and informally in the form of photos, and narratives or statements regarding services to tourists at the Kanto Lampo waterfall. This activity includes Russian, Japanese, Basic Mandarin training and local tourist guiding. The training participants were 30 staff who worked at the Kanto Lampo waterfall tourist attraction. Training is divided into 2 shifts, staff who work in the morning are given training in the afternoon and staff who work during the day are given training in the morning.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This community service activity began with a meeting with the manager of the Kanto Lampo waterfall tourist attraction to find out the problems faced and as a result of the discussion it was agreed to carry out K3 training, Russian, Mandarin and Japanese language training.

The first training was K3 training carried out 6 times given by K3 lecturers who already had K3 certificates. The training began with a pretest in the form of questions from the presenters about the use of K3 equipment and possible dangers that could occur at the Kanto Lampo waterfall tourist attraction. the results of the questions and answers in the pretest regarding K3, 30 percent of participants were able to answer how to use K3 equipment, 30 percent of participants were able to identify dangers that might occur in the Kanto Lampo waterfall tourist attraction. 40 percent of participants stated that they understood how to use K3 equipment and could identify possible dangers. After the training is carried out, it is necessary to measure the level of understanding of the importance of K3 through a post test. The posttest is given by asking questions to the participants. From the post test results, it can

be seen that 100 percent of participants can use K3 equipment and can find out or identify dangers that may occur at the Kanto Lampo waterfall.

Table 1. K3 Training Pre-Test and Post Test Results

Criteria	Respondent	
	Pretest (%)	Posttest (%)
Able to use K3 equipment	30	0
Can identify possible dangers	30	0
Can use K3 equipment and identify possible hazards	40	100

Based from data processed, 2023

Figure 1. Presenter K3, 2023

Apart from K3 training, community service at the Kanto Lampo tourist attraction is also carried out to improve staff skills through foreign language training. This aims to improve mastery of foreign languages such as Russian, Mandarin and Japanese. The results of the pre-test through question-and-answer materials stated that 70 percent had used grammar well, 30 percent had good intonation. Training is carried out proactively by starting with an example by the presenter and then followed by the participants. At the end of the training, participants are given a post test to determine their level of mastery of grammar and intonation in using a foreign language. The results of the posttest carried out by the presenters show that the use of good grammar has increased. From 70 percent to 87 percent can use grammar well. Intonation also increased to 100 percent.

Table 2. Foreign Language Training

Kriteria	Responden	
	Pre test (%)	Post test (%)
Penggunaan grammar	70	87
Intonasi	30	90

Based from data processed, 2023

Figure 2. Foreign Language Speaker, 2023

The level of achievement of foreign language training has not yet reached 100 percent because languages must be studied continuously. To get maximum results, further training and assistance is needed when staff carry out their activities. This is an evaluation of ongoing activities.

Figure 3. Evaluation of the activity, 2023

CONCLUSION

The community service activities carried out went very well. The increase in participants' understanding, skills and knowledge can be said to have increased significantly in both K3 training and foreign language training. This training needs to be carried out continuously both in the same field and in other fields because the staff will serve tourists.

REFERENCES

1. Bătinaş, R. H. (2010). The methodology for assessing the potential attractiveness of waterfalls as tourist attractions. *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai*, 2, 205-212.
2. Bekker, Barros, C. P., Botti, L., Peypoch, N., Robinot, E., Solonandrasana, B., & A., G. A. (2011). Performance of French destinations: Tourism attraction perspectives. *Tourism Management*, 32(1), 141–146. doi:10.1016/j.tourman.2010.01.015
3. Erhan Summak, M. (2014). A Study on the communication and emphatic skills of the students having education on tourism sector. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, (31), 131-137.
4. Gruescu, R., Nanu, R., & Tanasie, A. (2009). Human resources development and ICT contribution to the tourist destination competitiveness.
5. Hudson, B. J. (2013). *Waterfall: nature and culture*. Reaktion Books.

6. Noor, I. H. (2010). Penelitian dan pengabdian masyarakat pada perguruan tinggi. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Kebudayaan*, 16(3), 285-297.
7. Prasetyo, H. D., Hakim, L., & Retnaningdyah, C. (2017). Evaluating environmental service of trisula waterfall as nature-based tourism attraction in Bromo Tengger Semeru National Park. *Journal of Indonesian Tourism and Development Studies*, 5(2), 101-106.
8. Setyanto, A., & Litt, M. (2014). Pentingnya penguasaan bahasa dan budaya asing sebagai pendukung utama sektor pariwisata. *Jurnal Pariwisata: FIB Universitas Brawijaya*, 1(1), 1-12.

Cite this Article: I Nyoman Winia, Ni Nyoman Triyuni, Nyoman Mastiani Nadra, Ni Putu Lianda Ayu Puspita, Luh Putu Candra Aprilia Dewi (2023). Improving Staff Communication through Foreign Language Training on the Kanto Lampo Waterfall Tourist Attraction. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(10), 6556-6560